

2,4-Bis(Arylamino)-6-Methyl Pyrimidines as Antimicrobial Agents

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Nine 2,4-bis(arylamino) pyrimidines having $-\text{CH}_3$ substitution either in C-5 or C-6 in the pyrimidine ring have been synthesized. All these compounds have been tested against some gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and a pathogenic strain of yeast, *Candida albicans* for their antimicrobial activity. 2,4-bis(*p*-chloro-anilino)- and 2,4-bis(*p*-bromo-anilino) pyrimidine derivatives have been found to possess significant activity.

In our previous communications¹ it has been shown that 2,4-bis(arylamino)- and 2,4-bis(aryloxy) pyrimidines are potent antimicrobial and antifungal agents. Our further biological studies with these compounds indicate that 2,4-bis(arylamino) pyrimidines act as a partial uncoupler of oxydative phosphorylation². Encouraged by these findings we have prepared another series of 2,4-bis(arylamino) pyrimidines.

In this communication we wish to report the synthesis of compounds of type I, where $\text{R}_1 = -\text{CH}_3$, $\text{R}_2 = -\text{H}$ or $\text{R}_1 = \text{H}$ and $\text{R}_2 = \text{H}$

or $-\text{CH}_3$, and an evaluation of their growth inhibitory properties. These synthetic pyrimidines have been tested against some gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria and a pathogenic strain of yeast, *Candida albicans*, and their growth inhibitory activity has been compared with that of some known antibiotics and active synthetic compounds.

The 2,4-bis(arylamino) pyrimidines were synthesised by the acid catalysed condensation of 2,4-dichloro-^{3a} 2,4-dichloro-5-methyl-^{3b} and 2,4-dichloro-6-methyl-^{3c} pyrimidines with the appropriate aromatic amines.

Experimental

General method of synthesis of 2,4-bis(arylamino) pyrimidines: 2,4-Dichloro-pyrimidine derivatives (0.01 mole) in 5 ml ethanol was added dropwise with shaking to a warm solution of the appropriate amine (0.03 mole) in 2.7 ml of conc. HCl in 20 ml water. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on

TABLE I—2,4-BIS(ARYLAMINO)-6-METHYL PYRIMIDINES

Compd	R ₁	R ₂	Ar	Yield % (Crude)	Reaction ^a time, hr	m. p. °C ^b	Solvent of recrystn ^c
I	CH ₃	H	C ₆ H ₅	80	4	295-236	1N HCl
II	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	85	6	300	1N HCl
III	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	92	4	142-143	Aq. EtOH
IV	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	90	4	94-95	Aq. EtOH
V	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	96	4	266	EtOH
VI	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	96	2	>300	DMF
VII	CH ₃	H	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	95	4	159-160	EtOH
VIII	CH ₃	H	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	90	6	105	1N HCl
IX	H	H	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	96	0.5	240-241	EtOH
X	H	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	92	1	195-197	EtOH

^a In the synthesis of compound IX catalytic amount (0.2 ml) of conc. HCl was added.

^b All melting points were determined in capillary tubes in Gallen-Kump apparatus and are corrected.

^c DMF = Dimethyl formamide.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL RESULTS

Compound	Molecular formula	% carbon		% hydrogen		% nitrogen	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
I	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ .HCl	65.28	64.96	5.12	5.45	17.91	17.70
II	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ .HCl	59.50	59.12	4.60	5.06	16.22	15.89
III	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	67.85	67.95	5.95	6.05	16.60	16.44
IV	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₄	75.00	74.80	6.67	6.12	18.42	18.25
V	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	50.74	50.43	4.47	4.39	20.89	20.56
VI	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	55.73	55.85	3.82	4.06	22.95	22.63
VII	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄	47.00	46.78	3.22	3.29	12.90	12.63
VIII	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ .HCl	53.73	53.41	3.93	4.29	14.09	13.86
IX	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Br ₂ N ₄	45.71	45.26	2.85	2.85	13.33	13.05
X	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ Br ₂ N ₄	47.00	47.20	3.22	3.32	12.90	12.84

a sand bath until completion of the reaction (see Tables 1 and 2) and was kept overnight in the refrigerator. The crystalline product was filtered off and washed with cold water. It was then resuspended in about 30 ml of water, neutralised with dil. NH₄OH, cooled and collected as free base and recrystallised from suitable solvents.

Some compounds were recrystallised as hydrochlorides since they could not be satisfactorily crystallised as free bases.

Inhibition of growth of microorganisms : All compounds were tested for their antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli* B, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Vibrio cholerae* and a pathogenic strain of yeast, *Candida albicans*. The minimal concentrations of the synthetic compounds necessary for inhibition of growth at 24 hr were determined (Table 3). 2,4-Bis(*p*-nitro-anilino)-6-methyl pyrimidine(VI) could not be tested for antimicrobial activity due to low solubility of the compound. The inhibitory activity of these compounds have been compared with some well known antibiotics and other 2,4-bis(anilino) pyrimidine derivatives.

Results

Substitution of methyl group in the 6 position of pyrimidine ring does not show any significant difference in biological activities against microorganisms compared to 6-unsubstituted bis(aryl-amino) pyrimidines^{1c}. It is also noticeable (Table 3) that the biological activity depends on the substitution in the phenyl ring, which is in the order *p*-Cl > *p*-Br > *o*-Cl > *p*-CH₃ > *p*-SO₂NH₂ > *p*-OCH₃ > H > *p*-OH. All the arylaminopyrimidines tested by us so far, *p*-chloro-anilino and *p*-bromo-anilino derivatives have been the most biologically active ones^(1b,1c,1d).

TABLE 3—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF 2,4-Bis(ARYLAMINO)-6-METHYL PYRIMIDINES

Compd.	Minimum inhibitory concn. µg/ml				
	<i>S. faecalis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i> B	<i>Vibrio cholerae</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>
I	7.00	11.00	8.50	5.00	27.00
II	8.00	30.00	40.00	32.00	96.00
III	4.00	3.50	3.50	4.00	5.50
IV	2.00	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.50
V	3.00	4.00	4.00	4.50	5.00
VII	1.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	2.00
VIII	3.50	5.00	5.00	3.50	4.00
IX	1.50	2.00	2.00	3.00	1.50
X	2.00	3.00	3.50	3.00	3.00
2,4-Bis(<i>p</i> -chloro-anilino)pyrimidine	1.00	1.50	2.50	2.00	2.50
2,4-Bis(<i>p</i> -chloro-anilino)-6-methyl pyrimidine	1.00	1.50	2.50	2.00	2.50
2,4-Bis(<i>p</i> -chloro-anilino)-5 methyl pyrimidine	1.00	2.50	3.00	3.00	2.50
Chloramphenicol	2.50	3.00	2.00	0.50	a
Tetracycline	a	0.50	1.00	1.50	a
Streptomycin	a	1.00	3.00	10.00	a
Neomycin	a	0.50	1.50	10.00	a

a Little or no activity.

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